

ADVERSARIAL NETWORK BASED CLASSIFICATION FOR ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE USING MULTIMODAL BRAIN IMAGES

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Abstract: Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder that significantly impacts cognitive functions and remains a global health challenge. Early and accurate diagnosis is essential for effective intervention, yet traditional methods face limitations in precision and scalability. The project aims to extract and represent crucial features from these imaging modalities to achieve high classification accuracy. We propose BGAN (Brain-PET Generative Adversarial Network), an advanced framework designed to map MRI scans to their corresponding PET scans in an end-to-end manner. The methodology focuses on improving the quality and accuracy of synthetic PET images while preserving the unique brain structures of individual subjects. The experimental results of this study demonstrate that the proposed BPGAN framework effectively synthesizes high-quality PET images from MRI scans, preserving essential structural and functional details. Quantitative metrics such as SSIM and PSNR, alongside qualitative visualizations, validate the superiority of the synthetic PET images in terms of fidelity and accuracy.

Keywords: BGAN (Brain-PET Generative Adversarial Network), SSIM and PET.

1. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive and irreversible brain disorder that impairs memory and cognitive abilities, ultimately interfering with daily activities and diminishing an individual's independence. By 2050, nearly 150 million people are projected to be affected by AD, leading to substantial medical and economic challenges. Despite advancements in research, there is currently no treatment capable of halting or reversing the progression of the disease. This emphasizes the critical need for robust and accurate methods to facilitate the early detection of AD, which can help mitigate irreversible memory loss.

Recent advancements in machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have paved the way for improved medical imaging techniques to evaluate AD severity under diverse conditions using images from various modalities. Neuroimaging approaches, such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Positron Emission Tomography (PET), have proven effective in AD analysis. MRI, a non-invasive imaging technique, provides detailed insights into internal body structures like shape, size, and localization, offering high-quality images with excellent soft tissue contrast. MRI imaging is broadly categorized into functional and structural types,

with functional imaging further divided into task-based and resting-state functional MRI, while structural imaging includes T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and diffusion tensor imaging. On the other hand, PET imaging focuses on functional aspects, offering precise insights into brain activity, which makes it valuable for early AD diagnosis.

Feature extraction and representation play a critical role in medical image analysis, with DL-based methods emerging as preferred solutions due to their superior robustness and accuracy. Unlike traditional techniques, which often require extensive domain expertise, DL models can autonomously learn and extract features relevant to specific applications, making them particularly effective in identifying and classifying brain disorders. Furthermore, DL models can identify and combine essential features, enhancing their utility in predicting and classifying severe conditions like AD. This capability enables timely intervention by supporting early detection and diagnosis. Despite the significant progress achieved through AI-based methods, certain challenges persist. AD diagnosis often involves multi-class classification, and the presence of highly correlated features in brain structures can complicate the process. This paper presents a comparative study on the identification and classification of AD into two severity classes using 2D and 3D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The study includes training models on 829 samples comprising 2D MRI, 2D PET, 2D MRI-PET fusion, 3D MRI, 3D PET, and 3D MRI-PET fusion images. These datasets represent subjects with varying levels of disease severity, classified into two distinct categories.

II. OBJECTIVE

The objective of this project is to design and implement an adversarial network-based classification framework for the early detection and severity classification of Alzheimer's disease (AD) using multimodal brain images, including MRI, PET, and their fused representations. By leveraging the strengths of adversarial networks, the project aims to extract and represent crucial features from these imaging modalities to achieve high classification accuracy. A key focus is to integrate the complementary information provided by MRI and PET images through multimodal fusion techniques, enhancing the robustness and sensitivity of the classification system.

The study will compare the performance of 2D and 3D convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in analyzing these multimodal datasets, assessing their ability to handle different image dimensions and structures effectively. Additionally, the adversarial network will address challenges posed by highly correlated features in brain structures, enabling the model to identify patterns that signify AD progression more reliably. By developing a robust and accurate diagnostic tool, this project aims to facilitate early detection of AD, allowing timely medical intervention to slow cognitive decline. Furthermore, it seeks to demonstrate the potential of combining adversarial learning with multimodal imaging in advancing AI-driven approaches for neurodegenerative disease diagnosis, ultimately contributing to the future of healthcare innovation.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

Dementia is one of the huge medical problems that have challenged the public health sector around the world. Moreover, it generally occurred in older adults (age > 60). Shockingly, there are no legitimate drugs to fix this sickness, and once in a while it will directly influence individual memory abilities and diminish the human capacity to perform day by day exercises. Many health experts and computing scientists were performing research works on this issue for the most recent twenty years. All things considered, there is an immediate requirement for finding the relative characteristics that can figure out the identification of dementia. The motive behind the works presented in this thesis is to propose the sophisticated supervised machine learning model in the prediction and classification of AD in elder people. For that, we conducted different experiments on open access brain image information including demographic MRI data of 373 scan sessions of 150 patients. In the first two works, we applied single ML models called support vectors and pruned decision trees for the prediction of dementia on the same dataset.

In the first experiment with SVM, we achieved 70% of the prediction accuracy of late-stage dementia. Classification of true dementia subjects (precision) is calculated as 75%. Similarly, in the second experiment with J48 pruned decision trees, the accuracy was improved to the value of 88.73%. Classification of true dementia cases with this model was comprehensively done and achieved 92.4% of precision. To enhance this work, rather than single modelling we employed multi-modelling approaches. In the comparative analysis of the

machine learning study, we applied the feature reduction technique called principal component analysis. This approach identifies the high correlated features in the dataset that are closely associated with dementia type. By doing the simultaneous application of three models such as KNN, LR, and SVM, it has been possible to identify an ideal model for the classification of dementia subjects. When compared with support vectors, KNN and LR models comprehensively classified AD subjects with 97.6% and 98.3% of accuracy respectively. These values are relatively higher than the previous experiments. However, because of the AD severity in older adults, it should be mandatory to not leave true AD positives.

For the classification of true AD subjects among total subjects, we enhanced the model accuracy by introducing three independent experiments. In this work, we incorporated two new models called Naïve Bayes and Artificial Neural Networks along support vectors and KNN. In the first experiment, models were independently developed with manual feature selection. The experimental outcome suggested that KNN 3 is the optimal model solution because of 91.32% of classification accuracy. In the second experiment, the same models were tested with limited features (with high correlation). SVM was produced a high 96.12% of classification accuracy and NB produced a 98.21% classification rate of true AD subjects. Ultimately, in the third experiment, we mixed these four models and created a new model called hybrid type modelling. Hybrid model performance is validated AU-ROC curve value which is 0.991 (i.e., 99.1% of classification

accuracy) has achieved. All these experimental results suggested that the ensemble modelling approach with wrapping is an optimal solution in the classification of AD subjects.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGN

Several existing methods have been developed for the classification of Alzheimer's disease (AD) using brain imaging techniques. Traditional approaches often rely on manual or semi-automated feature extraction from imaging modalities such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Positron Emission Tomography (PET). These features are then analyzed using machine learning algorithms like Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Random Forests, or k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN) to classify AD severity. However, these methods depend heavily on domain expertise for feature selection and often lack the ability to generalize to diverse datasets.

In recent years, deep learning approaches, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have become popular for AD detection due to their ability to automatically extract relevant features. 2D and 3D CNNs have been employed to process slices or volumes of MRI and PET images, offering improved accuracy compared to traditional methods. Multimodal approaches that combine MRI and PET data have also shown promise, as they leverage complementary information from both modalities. Despite these advancements, existing methods face challenges such as overfitting, inability to handle highly correlated features, and difficulty in differentiating subtle patterns associated with AD progression.

The proposed system aims to overcome the challenges of existing methods by introducing a robust and efficient framework based on **Brain-**

PET Generative Adversarial Network (BPGAN) for synthesizing PET scans and classifying Alzheimer's disease (AD) using multimodal brain imaging data. This approach integrates MRI and synthetic PET modalities, exploiting their structural and functional complementarities to enhance diagnostic precision. The system incorporates both 2D and 3D convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to analyze imaging data, with a focus on evaluating their relative performance for different imaging modalities and fusion techniques. The core of the framework lies in the **3D Multiple Convolution U-Net (MCU) generator architecture**, designed to synthesize high-quality PET scans from MRI inputs while preserving intricate structural details unique to each subject. The generator is trained within an adversarial setup that includes a discriminator to iteratively improve the quality of synthetic PET images, ensuring realism and diagnostic relevance. To address challenges like feature correlation and subtle pattern differentiation in AD severity, the framework employs advanced loss functions, including **3D Gradient Profile (GP) Loss** and **Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) Loss**, to optimize feature extraction and enhance synthetic image quality.

The fusion of MRI and synthetic PET images creates a richer feature space, enabling more robust classification of AD severity. This multimodal approach leverages complementary information, improving the system's capacity to detect early signs of neurodegeneration. The framework is validated using a dataset of 829 multimodal brain images, categorized into two classes of AD severity. By combining adversarial learning with multimodal imaging fusion, the proposed system significantly improves

classification accuracy and demonstrates the potential of AI-driven solutions in advancing early diagnosis and treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

V.METHODOLOGY

We propose BPGAN (Brain-PET Generative Adversarial Network), an advanced framework designed to map MRI scans to their corresponding PET scans in an end-to-end manner. The methodology focuses on improving the quality and accuracy of synthetic PET images while preserving the unique brain structures of individual subjects.

GENERATOR ARCHITECTURE: The core of BPGAN is a 3D Multiple Convolution U-Net (MCU) generator, which uses an encoder-decoder structure enhanced with multiple convolutional layers. This design facilitates effective feature extraction and reconstruction, ensuring the synthetic PET images retain fine details and anatomical consistency across varying subjects.

LOSS FUNCTIONS: To optimize the quality of the generated PET scans: 3D Gradient Profile (GP) Loss is employed to ensure the synthetic PET images maintain edge consistency and gradients similar to the ground truth. Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) Loss is incorporated to enhance the overall perceptual quality, ensuring better resemblance to the true PET scans.

ALTERNATIVE DATA PARTITIONING: To evaluate the robustness of BPGAN in diverse medical scenarios, the study examines different data partitioning methods. By exploring these partitioning techniques, the performance of the model is analyzed under varied training and testing conditions, simulating real-world scenarios.

SYNTHETIC IMAGE GENERATION: The methodology focuses on producing high-quality synthetic PET images that can be used to supplement existing datasets, reduce reliance on expensive PET scans, and improve diagnostic performance when integrated with multimodal approaches.

VI. CONCLUSION

The experimental results of this study demonstrate that the proposed **BPGAN** framework effectively synthesizes high-quality PET images from MRI scans, preserving essential structural and functional details. Quantitative metrics such as SSIM and PSNR, alongside qualitative visualizations, validate the superiority of the synthetic PET images in terms of fidelity and accuracy. The complementary information derived from these synthetic PET scans enhances the performance of Alzheimer's disease (AD) diagnosis, showcasing the practical utility of the approach in clinical and research settings. By reducing dependency on expensive PET imaging and utilizing readily available MRI scans, BPGAN serves as a cost-effective and non-invasive alternative for multimodal medical image analysis. This work establishes a robust foundation for integrating generative adversarial networks in medical imaging tasks, offering valuable insights and references for future advancements in multimodal image synthesis and analysis.

VII.REFERENCE

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